

Relationship between Self-Compassion, Hope and Life Satisfaction among Late Adults: A Mediational Model

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Article Info	Abstract
<p>Article History</p> <p>Received: July 17 ,2023</p> <p>Accepted: October 18 ,2023</p> <hr/> <p>Keywords : Self-Compassion, Hope, Life Satisfaction, Middle Adults, Late Adults</p> <p>DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.10015830</p>	<p><i>The present study aimed to examine the relationship between self-compassion, hope and life satisfaction among late adults. Sample of the present study consisted of (N = 400) late adults recruited from Sargodha and Islamabad, Punjab, Pakistan. Data was gathered through convenient sampling technique by using survey research design. The variables of present study were operationalized through standardized Urdu translated instruments i.e. Self-Compassion Scale Short Form (Khan, 2017), Adult Hope Scale (Siddique&Hanif, 2021), and Satisfaction with Life Scale (Butt et al., 2014) to measure self-compassion, hope and life satisfaction respectively. Descriptive and psychometric properties were ensured. Correlation was performed which revealed significant correlations among variables of the present study in expected directions. The findings revealed significant mediating role of hope in relationship between self-compassion and life satisfaction among late adults. Implications of the study along with its limitations were discussed and recommendations for future research were suggested.</i></p>

Introduction

Self-compassion entails treating yourself with the same consideration, concern, and support that you would extend to a good friend (Neff&Dahm, 2015). Two cross-sectional studies have investigated the relationship between self-compassion and hope in healthy adults (Yang et al., 2016) and children (Neff & Faso, 2015). Both studies demonstrated that self-compassion was associated with both hope and life-satisfaction in positive direction. Further, in one of these studies, hope was found to fully mediate the relationship between self-compassion and life-satisfaction (Yang et al., 2016).

In Korea, 203 late adults over 65 were found to have higher life satisfaction when they practiced self-compassion. According to Kim and Ko (2018), self-compassion is beneficial for late adults' mental health outcomes and healthy aging. Kim and Ko (2018) suggested that late adults were more likely to engage in self-judgment and feel excluded and hope played a crucial role in improving the well-being of such individuals. Even though older people with low self-compassion and those with high self-compassion encountered identical age-related events, those with high self-compassion thought about these events in ways that indicated favorable outcomes. Encouragement of self-compassion in older people may increase their well-being in old life (Allen & Leary, 2012). Self-compassion enhances older people's mental health outcomes and good ageing. Also, self-compassionate older persons are more accepting of the hardships that come with the natural course of ageing, which may keep them from getting depressed hence, leading to more life satisfaction (Kim &Ko, 2018). Self-compassion seems to be strongly related with life satisfaction in any age group, including older adults (Kim &Ko, 2018).

Self-compassion can play a significant role in fostering hope in older adults. As people age, they may face various challenges, such as declining physical health, loss of loved ones, or changes in social roles. Self-compassion can help to create hope in late adults in such a way that they can cope better with adversities and reduce self-criticism. It helps them to build resilience, embrace change, enhance mental well-being and cultivate gratitude. Self-compassion enables individuals to have an unbiased mindset towards themselves, which helps individuals identify desirable life aims and boosts perceived confidence in creating achievable paths to those objectives (Sears & Kraus, 2009). Snyder et al. (1991) defined hope as the capacity of humans to establish clear goals (goals thinking), create pathways to achieving those goals (pathway thinking), and start to maintain the encouragement for employing those pathways (agency thinking). Hope in particular forecasts a hopeful association between life satisfaction and self-compassion. That is, through their amount of hope, an individual's level of self-compassion impacts their degree of overall life satisfaction (Yang et al., 2016). Higher levels of positive thinking and goal-related motivation may lead to increased life satisfaction, which is consistent with earlier findings (Gilman et al., 2006; Marques et al., 2013). Self-compassion has been linked to a number of positive outcomes, including higher levels of life satisfaction and well-being (Neff &Germer, 2017; Neff

&McGehee, 2010; Yang et al., 2016) and lower levels of negative emotions (Arimitsu & Hofmann, 2017; Neff et al., 2018).

The current research aims to explore the relationship between self-compassion, hope and life satisfaction among late adults, shedding light on the potential benefits of cultivating self-compassion and fostering hope during late adulthood. Late adulthood is a critical stage in the human lifespan, characterized by various challenges and transitions. Individuals in this stage often face significant life changes such as retirement, declining health, and loss of loved ones. Understanding the factors that contribute to their well-being and life satisfaction is crucial for promoting healthy aging. By fostering self-compassion and cultivating hope, interventions and programs can empower individuals in this life stage to navigate challenges, maintain resilience, and enhance their overall life satisfaction. Self-compassion enhances older people's mental health outcomes and good ageing. Also, self-compassionate older persons are more accepting of the hardships that come with the natural course of ageing, which may keep them from getting depressed hence, leading to more life satisfaction (Kim & Ko, 2018). Self-compassion seems to be strongly related with life satisfaction in any age group, including older adults (Kim & Ko, 2018). Though there isn't much work done on the impact of self-compassion and hope on life satisfaction in Pakistan, there still are studies available studying the impact of said variables independently. Self-compassion is positively linked with psychological well-being among university students of Pakistan (Abbasi & Zubair, 2015).

Objectives of present study

1. To examine the mediating role of hope in relationship between self-compassion and life satisfaction among late adults.

Hypotheses of present study

On the basis of aforementioned objective following hypotheses are formulated.

1. Self-compassion will be a significant positive predictor of hope among late adults.
2. Self-compassion will be a significant positive predictor of life satisfaction among late adults.
3. Hope will be a significant positive predictor of life satisfaction among late adults.
4. The relationship between self-compassion and life satisfaction will be mediated by hope among late adults.

Method

In the present study, a cross-sectional research design was used to measure the relationship between self-compassion, hope and life satisfaction among late adults by using the convenient sampling technique. A sample of ($N = 400$) with age range of 60 to 90 was collected from the Punjab region. This study was conducted based on the ethical principles outlined by Institutional Ethics Committee (IEC) and approved by the University Research Ethics Committee.

Instruments

Self-Compassion Scale Short Form (SCS-SF)

The Self-Compassion Scale – Short Form (Raes et al., 2011) is a 12 item self-report measure. In the present study its Urdu translated version is used, developed by Khan (2017) in an unpublished dissertation. The items in this scale are rated on 5-point Likert scale ranged from 1 (almost never) to 5 (almost always). SCS-SF has two subscales: self-disparagement and self-care. Self-disparagement covers items 1, 4, 8, 9, 11 and 12 and is an indication of how the client sees themselves regarding impatience, disapproval and judgment toward themselves. Higher score indicates higher self-criticism. The second sub-scale, self-care, covers items 2, 3, 5, 6, 7 and 10 and shows how clients see themselves with regard to tenderness, patience and empathy. Higher score indicates self-compassion. The reverse coded items are 1, 4, 8, 9, 11, and 12.

The global SCS-SF score had high internal consistency ($\alpha = .86$) (Raes et al., 2011). The internal consistencies for the subscales of Self-Compassion Scale Short-Form were relatively low (ranged between 0.54 and 0.75) and it was not recommended to use subscale interpretation for the SCS-SF. The test-retest reliability over a span of five months was found to be .71 (Raes et al., 2011). Alpha reliability of Urdu translated version of SCS-SF is .80 (Imtiaz, 2016).

Adult Hope Scale (AHS)

Adult Hope Scale (Synder et al., 1991) Urdu translated version is used in the present study (Siddique&Hanif, 2021). This instrument consists of 12 items rated on 8-point Likert scale. The score “1” indicates “definitely false”, while “8” indicates “definitely true”. Items 2, 9, 10, and 12 make up the agency subscale and items 1, 4, 6, and 8 make up the pathway subscale. Items 3, 5, 7, 11 are lie detectors and are ignored during data analysis.

Adult Hope Scale is highly reliable scale with alpha reliability of ($\alpha = 0.91$). Test-retest correlations have been .80 or above over periods exceeding 10 weeks (Synder et al., 1991). The alpha reliability of the Urdu translated version is 0.64 (Zubair, 2013).

Satisfaction with Life Scale (SWLS)

The SWLS was developed by Diener et al. (1985). It is a short 5-item instrument which is designed to measure people’s judgment of satisfaction with their life. The original scale is in the English language but Urdu translated version (Butt et al., 2014) was used for the convenience of Urdu speaking participants. The items of SWLS were rated on 7-point Likert scale ranged from 1 (strongly disagree) to 7 (strongly agree). This scale has no reverse coded items.

The Cronbach’s alpha ofSWLSranged from 0.83 to 0.86 (Shao et al., 2020). The Urdu version of the Satisfaction with Life Scale (SWLS-U) demonstrated a satisfactory inter-rater correlation (0.68), which enhances confidence in the scale’s alpha reliability. The computed alpha coefficient was determined to be $\alpha = 0.90$ (Hayat et al., 2016)

Results

Data was analyzed using Statistical Package for the Social Sciences (SPSS) 26. Descriptive statistics was calculated using mean and standard deviation. Normality of the data was assessed with skewness and kurtosis values. The instruments used in the survey were tested for internal reliability by calculating Cronbach’s alpha values. Correlations between the variables of interest were also calculated using Pearson correlation analysis. Finally, a Process Macro (Hayes, 2013) Model 4 was performed to determine the mediating role of hope in relationship between self-compassion and life satisfaction.

Table 1

Psychometrics, Descriptive, and Correlations of Continuous Variables (N = 400)

Variables	k	M	SD	α	Range		Skewness ^a	Kurtosis ^b	2	3
					Actual	Potential				
SC	12	40.9	7.4	.70	19-58	12-60	-.22	-.21	.51**	.44**
Hope	8	50.8	9.2	.86	9-64	8-64	-1.2	1.97	-	.58**
LS	5	23.9	6.6	.85	6-35	5-35	-.38	-.57	-	-

Note: SC = self-compassion; LS= Life satisfaction ** ($p < .01$)

Standard error^a = .12; Standard error^b = .24

Table 1 displays means, standard deviations, ranges, skewness, kurtosis, and alpha coefficients for each instrument utilized in the current research. The ratio between the values of skewness and standard error is less than 2, which suggests that variables are symmetrical in their distribution. The ratio between the values of kurtosis and standard error also shows symmetrical distribution. Actual and potential range depicts that it is not restricted to range and is showing appropriate variability. All scales lie in acceptable range. The reliability analysis indicates that the reliability coefficient of self-compassion, hope and life satisfaction scale are .70, .86, and .85 respectively which indicates favorable internal consistency.

Table 1 also suggests that self-compassion has significant positive correlation with hope ($r = .51, p < .01$) and life satisfaction ($r = .44, p < .01$). Hope has significant positive correlation with life satisfaction ($r = .58, p < .01$).

Table 2

Direct and Indirect effects on relationship among Self-Compassion, Hope and Life Satisfaction (N = 400)

Outcome	Variables	Direct effects			Indirect effect		
		95% CI			95% CI		
		B	LL	UL	B	LL	UL
Hope	SC	.62***	.52	.73			
LS	SC	.17***	.09	.26	.21***	.16	.27

LS	Hope	.34***	.27	.41
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Note: SC = self-compassion; LS= life satisfaction; CI = confidence interval

*** $p < .001$

A mediation analysis was performed (PROCESS Model 4; Hayes, 2018) to test the mediation hypothesis of present study. Table 2 showed that self-compassion predicted hope ($t(398) = 11.7, p < .001$) in positive direction and explained 26 % variance in it ($R^2 = .26$). Table 2 also displayed significant direct effect of self-compassion ($t(397) = 4.33, p < .001$), and hope ($t(397) = 10.3, p < .001$) on life satisfaction in positive directions and both of these variables explained 36% variance in it ($R^2 = .36$). Furthermore, the results indicated that self-compassion demonstrated a significant indirect effect on life satisfaction transmitted through hope. Bootstrapping with a 95% confidence interval and 5,000 bootstrapped samples demonstrated that the indirect effect was significant (95% CI, .16 to .27). The bootstrapped confidence intervals did not include zero, establishing the significance of the mediation ($p < .001$; Hayes, 2018). In other words, hope mediated the relationship between self-compassion and life satisfaction. Therefore, the study hypothesis was supported (see Figure 1 for the mediation model).

Figure 1.

Mediation model for self-compassion, hope and life satisfaction, with unstandardized regression coefficients. c = total effect of self-compassion and life satisfaction. c' = direct effect of self-compassion on life satisfaction.

Discussion

The present study aimed to investigate the relationship between self-compassion, hope and life satisfaction among late adults. The analysis was conducted via SPSS V26. The main results of the current study are described in this part, but also underline their reasoning. Each finding was taken into consideration in the relevant literature, in order to bridge the gap in accessible investigation or complement the findings of additional experts. Data has supported hypotheses predicted in this study.

The results supported the first hypothesis of the present study i.e. self-compassion will be a significant positive predictor of hope among late adults. There is evidence in literature that links self-compassion with hope. As self-compassion requires kindness to oneself, our failures are viewed as opportunities for learning and mastery, rather than responding oneself with harsh self-criticisms (Neff et al., 2005). Being kind to oneself also involves doing things that can make one happy. Thus, self-compassionate individuals are more likely to take on challenging tasks and learning new skills that can lead toward achieving their goals, and are also more open to changing themselves for the better as they acknowledge their weaknesses (Neff & Dahm, 2015). The positive self-attitude and enhanced perception of competence that self-compassion promotes can facilitate the identification of desired goals, and assist in perceiving and sustaining higher motivation toward goals even in difficult situations, thereby increasing hope (Yang et al., 2016).

The results supported the second hypothesis of the present study i.e. self-compassion will be a significant positive predictor of life satisfaction among late adults. The results showed that higher the self-compassion, higher will be the life satisfaction. Literature is also in line with the findings of present study such as Neff and Seppala (2017) claim that people who practice more self-compassion are more likely to be satisfied with their lives. When self-compassion's components such as self-kindness, common humanity, and mindfulness are practiced more frequently, life satisfaction increases, whereas self-judgment and isolation are negatively connected with life satisfaction (Mülazım & Eldelekliolu, 2016). Positive correlations between authenticity, self-compassion, and a quiet ego and life satisfaction were reported (Chew & Ang, 2021). Wayment

et al. (2016) showed how those with a quieter ego were more inclined to create compassion-oriented objectives, to exercise better self-control, and to exhibit greater self-compassion, all of which reduce stress perception and improve quality of life. According to Rathi and Lee (2021) those who express their emotions more openly had higher levels of life satisfaction and psychological well-being.

The results of the present study supported the third hypothesis i.e. hope will be a significant positive predictor of life satisfaction among late adults. Telef (2020) reported that hope predicted positive affect and life satisfaction while negatively predicting negative affect. Hope and pleasant emotions are major factors in life satisfaction (Telef, 2020). Individuals with more level of life satisfaction experience higher level of hope (Karataş, 2021). While a high level of hope is associated with excellent health and full functioning, a low amount is associated with emotional melancholy and pain (Martin, 2007). People's assessments of their ability to attain their goals influence their moods, and believing that their efforts will result in success raises their level of hope. According to Rivera et al., 2021; hope is a key factor in resilience and life satisfaction. In terms of life satisfaction, it was shown that, in addition to the impacts of resilience, hope was positively correlated with life satisfaction. Hope is a construct with the potential to significantly and favorably impact life satisfaction of individuals, which is consistent with earlier findings (Bailey et al., 2007; Hirschi, 2014; Karaman et al., 2020).

The results also supported the last hypothesis of the study i.e. the relationship between self-compassion and life satisfaction will be mediated by hope among late adults. The results of present study shows that hope fully mediated the positive relationship between self-compassion and life satisfaction, indicating that hope is a particularly effective mediator underlying the positive relationship between self-compassion and life satisfaction. That is, how satisfied individuals are about their overall lives is not directly influenced by their levels of self-compassion, but indirectly through their levels of hope (Yang et al., 2016).

Conclusion

The present study investigated the relationship between self-compassion, hope and life satisfaction among middle and late adults. The findings revealed the similar trend as it was empirically established that self-compassion and hope were significant positive predictors of life satisfaction. These variables do so by promoting emotional well-being, resilience, motivation and effective coping strategies. These positive psychological factors empower individuals to navigate life's ups and downs with greater positivity which ultimately leads to greater life satisfaction.

The mediation analysis revealed significant mediating effect of hope in relationship between self-compassion and life satisfaction. Self-compassion fosters a positive self-perception and emotional well-being. This, in turn, enhances a person's sense of hope and belief in positive outcomes. Hope then contributes to better life satisfaction by motivating individuals and helping them set and pursue meaningful goals.

Limitations and Suggestions

The outcomes of the study may be weaker if certain concerns could not be controlled. It is important to acknowledge some limitations of the study and suggestions for future research.

1. The individuals had shown social desirability and response bias because many individuals were not interested in discussing their private information which may harm the results of the study. To minimize social desirability bias, anonymity should be ensured and also respondents should not be obligated to write their names on the survey forms.
2. Data was only collected from late adults living with families. Elders living in old homes could not be part of this study so results cannot be generalized on late adulthood. It is recommended that in future research; the sample should be extracted from diverse population and from different regions so it could be generalized.
3. In survey study, there are no ways and means to manage irrelevant as well as confounding variables, which constitute so far another limitation of the current study. It is also recommended that in future studies the sample also include more variables or moderating and mediating effects of variables.
4. Different variables like family background, life style, socioeconomic status can also influence life satisfaction of middle and late adults. The study did not control all these factors. For increasing the internal validity of the study, family background, socioeconomic status and life styles should be looked upon in the future.

Implications of the Present Study

To the most admirable of the researcher's understanding, this is an important research in Pakistan to explore the relationship between self-compassion, hope and life satisfaction among middle and late adults. The present study opens new horizon for researches for better understanding the nature of life satisfaction. It motivates them to understand the nature of needs and requirements of both middle and late adults and help them for further researches. As the study explored, self-compassion has a positive impact on life satisfaction and so does hope.

This study is used for the better understanding of the similarities of life events of middle and late adults. Clinicians can recognize their difficulties and develop solutions to enhance their level of self-compassion and hope. Relevant therapeutic measures could be identified to increase level of self-compassion and hope for enhancing the life satisfaction of the clients. This study adds to the little range of studies and could encourage academics to build a better and more accurate understanding of the complex interactions between causes and effects between variables of this study.

References

- Abbasi, A., & Zubair, A. (2015). Body image, self-compassion, and psychological well-being among university students. *Pakistan Journal of Social and Clinical Psychology, 13*(1), 41-45.
- Allen, A. B., Goldwasser, E. R., & Leary, M. R. (2012). Self-compassion and well-being among older adults. *Self and Identity, 11*(4), 428-453. <https://doi.org/10.1080/15298868.2011.595082>
- An, H. Y., Chen, W., Wang, C. W., Yang, H. F., Huang, W. T., & Fan, S. Y. (2020). The relationships between physical activity and life satisfaction and happiness among young, middle-aged, and older adults. *International Journal of Environmental Research and Public Health, 17*(13), 4817-4820. <https://doi.org/10.3390/ijerph17134817>
- Arimitsu, K., & Hofmann, S. G. (2017). Effects of compassionate thinking on negative emotions. *Cognition and Emotion, 31*(1), 160-167. <https://doi.org/10.1080/02699931.2015.1078292>
- Bailey, T. C., & Snyder, C. R. (2007). Satisfaction with life and hope: A look at age and marital status. *The Psychological Record, 57*(1), 233-240. <https://doi.org/10.1007/BF03395574>
- Chew, L. C., & Ang, C. S. (2023). The relationship among quiet ego, authenticity, self-compassion and life satisfaction in adults. *Current Psychology, 42*(7), 5254-5264. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s12144-021-01867-5>
- Diener, E. D., Emmons, R. A., Larsen, R. J., & Griffin, S. (1985). The satisfaction with life scale. *Journal of Personality Assessment, 49*(1), 71-75. https://doi.org/10.1207/s15327752jpa4901_13
- Gilman, R., & Huebner, E. S. (2006). Characteristics of adolescents who report very high life satisfaction. *Journal of youth and adolescence, 35*(1), 293-301. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s10964-006-9036-7>
- Hirschi, A. (2014). Hope as a resource for self-directed career management: Investigating mediating effects on proactive career behaviors and life and job satisfaction. *Journal of Happiness Studies, 15*(1), 1495-1512. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s10902-013-9488-x>
- Imtiaz, S. (2016). Rumination, optimism, and psychological well-being among the elderly: Self-compassion as a predictor. *Journal of Behavioural Sciences, 26*(1), 32-36.
- Johnson, E. A., & O'Brien, K. A. (2013). Self-compassion soothes the savage ego-threat system: Effects on negative affect, shame, rumination, and depressive symptoms. *Journal of Social and Clinical Psychology, 32*(9), 939-963. <https://doi.org/10.1521/jscp.2013.32.9.939>
- Karaman, M. A., Vela, J. C., & Garcia, C. (2020). Do hope and meaning of life mediate resilience and life satisfaction among Latinx students? *British Journal of Guidance & Counselling, 48*(5), 685-696. <https://doi.org/10.1080/03069885.2020.1760206>
- Karataş, Z., Uzun, K., & Tagay, Ö. (2021). Relationships between the life satisfaction, meaning in life, hope and COVID-19 fear for Turkish adults during the COVID-19 outbreak. *Frontiers in Psychology, 12*(1), 633-684. <https://doi.org/10.3389/fpsyg.2021.633384>
- Kim, C., & Ko, H. (2018). The impact of self-compassion on mental health, sleep, quality of life and life satisfaction among older adults. *Geriatric Nursing, 39*(6), 623-628. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.gerinurse.2018.06.005>
- Marques, S. C., Lopez, S. J., & Mitchell, J. (2013). The role of hope, spirituality and religious practice in adolescents' life satisfaction: Longitudinal findings. *Journal of Happiness Studies, 14*(1), 251-261. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s10902-012-9329-3>
- Mülazım, Ö. Ç., & Eldeleklioğlu, J. (2016). What is the role of self-compassion on subjective happiness and life satisfaction? *Journal of Human Sciences, 13*(3), 3895-3904. <http://orcid.org/0000-0003-0906-9242>
- Neff, K. D., & Dahm, K. A. (2015). *Self-compassion: What it is, what it does, and how it relates to mindfulness*. Handbook of mindfulness and self-regulation, *1*(2)121-137. https://doi.org/10.1007/978-1-4939-2263-5_10
- Neff, K. D., & Faso, D. J. (2015). Self-compassion and well-being in parents of children with autism. *Mindfulness, 6*(1), 938-947. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s12671-014-0359-2>
- Neff, K. D., & McGehee, P. (2010). Self-compassion and psychological resilience among adolescents and young adults. *Self and identity, 9*(3), 225-240. <https://doi.org/10.1080/15298860902979307>
- Nef, K. D., Tóth-Király, I., & Colosimo, K. (2018). Self-compassion is best measured as a global construct and is overlapping with but distinct from neuroticism: A response to Pfattheicher, Geiger, Hartung, Weiss, and Schindler (2017). *European Journal of Personality, 32*(1), 371-392. <https://doi.org/10.1002/per.2148>

- Raes, F., Pommier, E., Neff, K. D., & Van Gucht, D. (2011). Construction and factorial validation of a short form of the self-compassion scale. *Clinical Psychology & Psychotherapy*, 18(3), 250-255. <https://doi.org/10.1002/cpp.702>
- Rathi, N., & Lee, K. (2021). Does it pay to be authentic? Implications of authenticity for life satisfaction and psychological well-being in a collectivist culture. *Journal of Happiness Studies*, 22(1), 147-161. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s10902-020-00223-x>
- Rivera, M., Shapoval, V., & Medeiros, M. (2021). The relationship between career adaptability, hope, resilience, and life satisfaction for hospitality students in times of Covid-19. *Journal of Hospitality, Leisure, Sport & Tourism Education*, 29(1), 100344. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jhlste.2021.100344>
- Sears, S., & Kraus, S. (2009). I think therefore I am: Cognitive distortions and coping style as mediators for the effects of mindfulness meditation on anxiety, positive and negative affect, and hope. *Journal of clinical psychology*, 65(6), 561-573. <https://doi.org/10.1002/jclp.20543>
- Siddique, M. P., & Hanif, R. (2021). Better Late than Never: An Interplay of Hope and Child Schema Modes among Young Adults. *International Journal of Innovation, Creativity and Change*, 15(1), 1079-1090.
- Snyder, C. R., Harris, C., Anderson, J. R., Holleran, S. A., Irving, L. M., Sigmon, S. T., ... & Harney, P. (1991). The will and the ways: development and validation of an individual-differences measure of hope. *Journal of Personality and Social Psychology*, 60(4), 570-576. <https://psycnet.apa.org/doi/10.1037/0022-3514.60.4.570>
- Telef, B. B. (2020). Hope and life satisfaction in elementary school students: Mediation role of affective experiences. *Journal of Positive School Psychology*, 4(2), 176-186. <https://journalppw.com/index.php/jpsp/article/view/119>
- Wayment, H. A., West, T. N., & Craddock, E. B. (2016). Compassionate values as a resource during the transition to college: Quiet ego, compassionate goals, and self-compassion. *Journal of the First-Year Experience & Students in Transition*, 28(2), 93-114.
- Yang, Y., Zhang, M., & Kou, Y. (2016). Self-compassion and life satisfaction: The mediating role of hope. *Personality and Individual Differences*, 98(1), 91-95. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.paid.2016.03.086>
- Zubair, S. (2013). *Effect of music on quality of life, hopelessness and happiness in old age* [Unpublished master's dissertation]. University of Sargodha.

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